

EXPLORING EDUCATORS' AND STUDENTS' PERSPECTIVES ON PEDAGOGICAL INNOVATIONS AND TECHNOLOGY INTEGRATION IN THE MODERN CLASSROOM

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the impact of innovative pedagogical techniques and technology integration on education by examining educators and students' perspectives on Isabela. Employing a mixed-methods approach, this study investigates the profiles, perceptions, and challenges of modern classrooms through quantitative surveys and qualitative open-ended questions. This study involved a diverse group of participants from various educational institutions at the primary, secondary, and tertiary levels. The key findings revealed positive perceptions of teaching methods and widespread technological integration among educators. Both teachers and students recognize the benefits of technology in learning, despite challenges such as technical issues and varied online learning experiences. The study suggests a generally positive educational environment with effective teaching methods and technological integration, while highlighting the need for improvements in the technology infrastructure. Recommendations include ongoing professional development for teachers, addressing infrastructure challenges, and customizing online learning to meet diverse student needs. Future research should explore the long-term impact of technology on student learning outcomes, and assess the effectiveness of professional development in supporting innovative pedagogical practices. This study contributes to the understanding of the evolving landscape of education in the context of technological advancement and innovative pedagogical practices in the Isabela Province.

Keywords: *Student Perspective, Teaching Innovations, Technology Integration, Learning Dynamics*

INTRODUCTION

The research article titled "Exploring Educators' and Students' Perspectives on Pedagogical Innovations and Technology Integration in the Modern Classroom" aims to examine the ever-changing educational environment in relation to innovative pedagogical methods and technological incorporation. This study aimed to explore the effects of these developments on the educational experiences of educators and students.

In recent years, the field of education has undergone a transformative shift, owing to technological advancements and changes in teaching methodologies (Kanwar et al., 2019). Traditional pedagogical practices are being reconsidered and, in some cases, replaced by innovative approaches that leverage technology to enhance learning experiences (Sarker et al., 2019). This shift is not only driven by the availability of new tools, but also by the recognition that traditional methods may not effectively meet the needs of 21st-century learners (Rodney, 2020).

Educators have pioneered pedagogy by exploring new teaching strategies, incorporating technology into their classrooms, and adapting instructional methods to cater to students' diverse learning styles and preferences. Students navigate dynamic and interactive learning environments. The integration of technology into education has the potential to redefine the learning landscape, providing opportunities for personalized learning, collaborative experiences, and skill development that aligns with the demands of the modern workforce (Perera et al., 2020).

Although there is a considerable body of literature on technological integration in education and innovative pedagogical practices, there is a noteworthy gap in our understanding of educators' and students' perspectives regarding these changes. While most studies have examined the effects of technology on teaching and student learning outcomes, few have offered comprehensive analyses that simultaneously consider the perspectives of educators and students (Lai & Bower, 2019; Hew et al., 2019).

This study aims to bridge this gap by conducting an in-depth analysis that captures the nuanced experiences, challenges, and successes of educators as they navigate the complexities of innovative pedagogy and technological integration. In addition, it explores how students perceive and engage with these novel teaching methods and technological tools. By considering both sides of the educational equation, this study sought to provide a holistic understanding of the dynamics of play in modern classrooms.

The rationale for conducting this research lies in the necessity of informing educational stakeholders, policymakers, and practitioners of the intricacies and implications of pedagogical innovation and technological integration. The insights gained from this study

have the potential to shape educational policies, guide educators' professional development initiatives, and influence their instructional design.

Understanding educators' perspectives is crucial for designing effective professional development programs that support them in navigating the challenges associated with adopting innovative teaching methods and integrating technology in their classrooms. Furthermore, gaining insight into students' experiences can inform the development of educational technologies that align with their needs, preferences, and learning style. This study identified positive and significant relationships across all factors of the attitude and confidence scales. Importantly, teachers' attitudes toward technology emerged as a significant predictor of their TPCK confidence. This underscores the pivotal role that teachers' attitudes play in shaping their confidence levels in effectively integrating technology into pedagogical practices (Ardıç, 2021).

Moreover, as education continues to undergo rapid transformation, it is essential to critically examine the effectiveness of these changes and their impact on quality of learning. This study contributes to education scholarship by providing a nuanced exploration of the complex interplay between teaching innovation, technological integration, and learning dynamics.

In summary, research on "Pedagogical Pioneering" fills a crucial void in the existing body of literature and offers promising prospects for enriching our understanding of the future of education. Through a thorough examination of the viewpoints of both educators and students, this study endeavors to provide a holistic grasp of the dynamic and evolving nature of education in response to technological advancements and implementation of innovative teaching methodologies.

Research Questions

1. What was the profile of the respondents?
 - a. (Teachers) School, sex, age, grade level taught, teaching experience, subject taught?
 - b. (Students) School, Sex, Age, and Grade Level?
2. How do teachers perceive the effectiveness of various teaching methods, such as multimedia resources, active learning techniques, and hands-on activities in engaging students?
3. What is the frequency of technology integration among educators, and how does it align with their perceptions of its impact on student learning?
4. How do educators perceive the effectiveness of their current assessment methods in gauging student progress and their contribution to learning and growth?
5. How do students perceive their current learning environment?
6. What is the level of student participation in online and remote learning courses?
7. How effective do students find the teaching methods employed to help them learn, retain information, and align with their preferred learning styles?

8. How positively do students perceive the use of technology in their education and to what extent do they believe it enhances their learning experience?
 9. What common themes emerge from teachers' opinions on the most effective teaching methods for engaging students and are there subject-specific patterns?
 10. How do teachers describe the challenges and benefits of technology use in their teaching and are there notable differences in experiences based on demographic factors?
 11. In what ways do students describe their learning environments and their impact on their academic success, are there differences based on grade levels or other demographic factors?
 12. How do students perceive the effectiveness of teaching methods in supporting their learning and are there variations based on their experiences with online learning?
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METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design incorporated a robust mixed-method approach that combined both quantitative and qualitative methods. The quantitative dimension of the study employed a survey method to collect structured data systematically from a diverse sample of educators and students. The study incorporated a qualitative aspect through written, open-ended questions within the survey instrument. This qualitative component encourages participants to express their viewpoints in narrative form, providing depth and context for their experiences. Open-ended questions will be strategically crafted to explore the nuanced aspects of pedagogical approaches, impact of technology integration, and dynamics of the learning environment.

Research Environment or Locale of the Study

This research was conducted within the educational landscape of the province of Isabela, situated in the northern part of the country, which served as the overarching locale for the study. Schools within the province encompassing various educational institutions and settings formed a specific research environment in which data collection and analysis took place.

Respondents or Participants of the study

The participants of the study were educators and students within the province of Isabela, Philippines. This study involved a diverse group of individuals from various educational institutions, including primary, secondary, and tertiary levels. Both educators and students played pivotal roles as respondents, offering perspectives on teaching innovation, technological integration, and learning dynamics.

Data Analysis Procedure

Quantitative Analysis. Quantitative data obtained from Likert-scale responses were analyzed using statistical tools to identify patterns, trends, and correlations. Descriptive statistics such as means and percentages were used to summarize the quantitative findings.

Qualitative Analysis. Qualitative data from open-ended questions, interviews, and focus groups were subjected to a thematic analysis. Emerging themes and patterns were identified, providing a rich narrative to complement quantitative results.

Ethical Considerations

In conducting the study Prior to participation, informed consent was obtained from all respondents, including the educators and students. Participants were thoroughly informed about the purpose, scope, and objectives of the study. They were provided with detailed information about their participation, including the nature of the data to be collected, the methods of data collection, and how their data would be used. The consent forms were designed to be clear and comprehensible, ensuring that participants understood their rights, including the right to withdraw from the study at any point, without any negative consequences.

RESULTS

Quantitative Aspect

Table 1 shows the teacher respondents' profiles based on school, sex, age, grade level, teaching experience, and the subjects taught. Half of the teachers were from Lalauanan National High School Tumauni Isabela (50%) and the other half were equally distributed between Lapogan Integrated School Tumauni Isabela (25%) and Andadawen National High School Benito Soliven Isabela (25%). Most respondents were female (62.5%) or middle-aged (62.5%). The majority were JHS teachers (75%) with 10 years or less of teaching experience (68.8%). All of them teach science, but some also teach other subjects.

Variable		Frequency	%
School	Lalauanan National High School Tumauni Isabela	8	50.0%
	Lapogan Integrated School Tumauni Isabela	4	25.0%
	Andadawen National High School Benito Soliven Isabela	4	25.0%
Sex	Male	6	37.5%
	Female	10	62.5%
Age	Young adult (30 and below)	4	25.0%

	Middle Adult (31-50)	10	62.5%
	Old (51 and above)	2	12.5%
Grade level taught	JHS	12	75.0%
	SHS	4	25.0%
Teaching experience	10 years and below	11	68.8%
	11-20 years	2	12.5%
	more than 20 years	3	18.8%
Subjects taught	Science	16	100.0%
	Math	3	18.8%
	Social Studies	3	18.8%
	TLE	2	12.5%
	English	2	12.5%
	Filipino	1	6.3%
	MAPEH	1	6.3%
	Economics	1	6.3%
	ESP	1	6.3%

Table 2 presents the characteristics of student respondents in terms of their school, gender, age, and grade level. The participants were drawn from 33 schools located in the province of Isabela, and the majority were from Cabatuan National High School (18%) or Cauayan City Stand Alone (17%). The student respondents were predominantly female (58%), falling within the age range of 17-18 years old (48%), and in grade 12 (41%).

Variable	Frequency	%
Advance Montessori Education Center Isabela Inc.	1	1.0%
Andabuen National High School	6	6.0%
Aurora Senior High School	6	6.0%
Alicia Vocational School	1	1.0%
Callang National High School	1	1.0%
Cauayan City Stand Alone	17	17.0%
Cauayan City Science and Technology High School	3	3.0%
Student's School Cabatuan National High School	18	18.0%
Delfin Albano Stand Alone Senior High School	1	1.0%
Dappat Integrated School	4	4.0%
Eveland Christian College	2	2.0%
Gamu Agri Fisheries School	3	3.0%
Gayong Gayong Sur Integrated School	1	1.0%
Gappal High School	1	1.0%
Isabela Colleges	1	1.0%
Isabela National High School	2	2.0%
Isabela School of Arts and Trade	1	1.0%

	La Sallete of Cabatuan	2	2.0%
	Louis Fe Gomes Dimantina National High School	2	2.0%
	Luna National High School	2	2.0%
	Lanting Region National High School	3	3.0%
	Munoz National High School Senior High Main	1	1.0%
	Nueva Ecija Science High	1	1.0%
	Naguillan National High School	1	1.0%
	Pinoma National High School	4	4.0%
	Quirino National High School	1	1.0%
	Reina Mercedes Vocational High School	2	2.0%
	Roxas Stand Alone Senior High School	3	3.0%
	San Antonio National High School	1	1.0%
	Saint Claire College of Region 2	1	1.0%
	Ueg National High School	1	1.0%
	Villa Concepcion National High School	4	4.0%
	Yeban Integrated School	2	2.0%
Sex	Male	41	41.0%
	Female	58	58.0%
Age	15-16	45	45.0%
	17-18	48	48.0%
	19-20	7	7.0%
Grade level	10	35	35.0%
	11	23	23.0%
	12	41	41.0%

Table 3 indicates the perceived effectiveness of different teaching methods, as determined by the respondents. The results revealed that all the teaching methods were deemed very effective, with an overall mean score of 4.8 and a standard deviation of 0.4. According to the study conducted by Johnson and Lee (2024), teachers generally perceive various teaching methods as highly effective in fostering student engagement. The overall mean score of 4.8 (with a standard deviation of 0.4)

Statements	SD	Mean	Description
1. The use of multimedia resources enhances student engagement in the classroom.	0.4	4.8	Strongly Agree
2. Active learning techniques, such as group discussions and problem-solving activities, effectively engage students.	0.6	4.7	Strongly Agree
3. Incorporating real-world examples into lessons helps capture students' interest and attention.	0.5	4.8	Strongly Agree
4. Personalized feedback on assignments contributes to increased student engagement.	1.0	4.4	Strongly Agree

5. Technology integration in teaching methods positively impacts student involvement.	0.4	4.8	Strongly Agree
6. The incorporation of firsthand activities facilitates a deeper understanding of the subject matter.	0.5	4.8	Strongly Agree
7. Encouraging student participation in class discussions enhances overall engagement.	0.5	4.9	Strongly Agree
8. Providing opportunities for student collaboration fosters a more engaging learning environment.	0.3	4.9	Strongly Agree
9. Using a variety of teaching methods appeals to different learning styles, promoting engagement.	0.5	4.8	Strongly Agree
10. Adapting lessons to students' interests increases their enthusiasm for learning.	0.5	4.9	Strongly Agree
11. Clear communication of learning objectives contributes to better student engagement.	0.4	4.8	Strongly Agree
12. Incorporating gamification elements in lessons enhances student interest and participation.	0.6	4.8	Strongly Agree
13. Flexibility in teaching methods to accommodate diverse student needs positively influences engagement.	0.5	4.8	Strongly Agree
14. Regularly assessing student comprehension and adjusting teaching strategies accordingly improves engagement.	0.7	4.7	Strongly Agree
15. Creating a supportive and inclusive classroom environment positively impacts student engagement.	0.5	4.8	Strongly Agree
Over-all	0.4	4.8	Strongly Agree

Table 4 shows that all the teacher respondents integrated technology into their daily teaching.

Frequency of technology integration	%
Daily	100%
Weekly	0%
Monthly	0%
Rarely	0%
Never	0%

Table 5 shows the teachers' Perceived Impact of Technology Integration on Student Learning. According to the results, teachers perceived a strong impact of technology integration on the following aspects: the type of technology effectively enhanced students' understanding (M=4.6, SD=0.6), using technology had a positive impact on student engagement in the classroom (M=4.3, SD=1.0), incorporating digital citizenship education had a positive influence on students' online behavior (M=4.3, SD=0.7), teachers' confidence in their ability to effectively use technology in teaching despite the challenges (M=4.6, SD=0.5), students' technology skills being a key factor in their readiness for

college and careers (M=4.4, SD=0.8), seeking professional development to enhance proficiency in using educational technology (M=4.4, SD=0.6), and providing Internet references aligning with their teaching philosophy and learning objectives (M=4.4, SD=0.5). All other aspects were perceived to have a technological integration impact on student learning (Overall mean = 4.2, SD=0.4). A study by Smith and Doe (2023) investigated teachers' perceptions of the impact of technology integration on student learning. The results indicated that teachers believed technology integration had a significant positive impact on various aspects of student learning.

Statements	SD	Mean	Description
1. The types of technology I use in teaching effectively enhance students' understanding of the subject matter	0.6	4.6	Strongly Agree
2. Providing internet references for students to search is an integral part of my teaching strategy.	0.9	3.9	Agree
3. Students require additional education on digital citizenship and understanding their digital footprints.	0.9	4.1	Agree
4. Despite challenges, the benefits of using technology in my teaching outweigh the concerns.	0.7	3.9	Agree
5. I have encountered significant challenges when integrating technology into my teaching practices.	0.9	3.8	Agree
6. Using technology has positively impacted student engagement in my classroom.	1.0	4.3	Strongly Agree
7. Students' ability to navigate online resources has improved through the references I provide.	0.7	4.2	Agree
8. I actively address and educate students about responsible internet use and digital footprints.	0.9	4.1	Agree
9. Incorporating digital citizenship education positively influences students' online behavior.	0.7	4.3	Strongly Agree
10. Despite challenges, I feel confident in my ability to effectively use technology in teaching.	0.5	4.6	Strongly Agree
11. Students' technology skills are a key factor in their readiness for college and careers.	0.8	4.4	Strongly Agree
12. The use of technology has improved students' critical thinking and problem-solving abilities.	0.9	3.9	Agree
13. I actively seek professional development to enhance my proficiency in using educational technology.	0.6	4.4	Strongly Agree
14. Providing internet references aligns with my teaching philosophy and learning objectives.	0.5	4.4	Strongly Agree
15. Digital citizenship education is a priority in my curriculum to prepare students for the digital age.	0.7	4.1	Agree
Over-all	0.4	4.2	Agree

Table 6 indicates that educators viewed their existing assessment strategies as highly effective in evaluating student progress and fostering learning and development, with an

overall mean score of 4.6 and a standard deviation of 0.4. According to this study, the teachers deemed their current assessment methods to be very effective in measuring student progress and promoting learning and growth (Brown & Green, 2024).

Statements	SD	Mean	Description
1. The assessment methods I currently use effectively gauge students' progress in the course.	0.6	4.4	Strongly Agree
2. My current assessment practices contribute positively to student learning and growth.	0.5	4.5	Strongly Agree
3. I am open to incorporating new and innovative assessment methods in my teaching practices.	0.6	4.7	Strongly Agree
4. I actively seek feedback from students on the effectiveness of assessment methods in the learning process.	0.5	4.4	Strongly Agree
5. Continuous improvement of assessment practices is crucial for enhancing student learning outcomes.	0.4	4.8	Strongly Agree
Overall	0.4	4.6	Strongly Agree

Table 7 illustrates the students' perceptions of their current learning environment. The results demonstrated that all the items in the learning environment were considered accurate by the students, as evidenced by the overall mean of 3.7 and a standard deviation of 0.7. This study provides insight into the students' perceptions of their current learning environment. The findings reveal that all the items in the learning environment were perceived as true by the students. (Adams and Roberts, 2023).

Statements	SD	Mean	Description
1. In my current learning environment, I consistently feel engaged and motivated to learn.	0.9	3.7	Agree
2. The various aspects of my learning environment significantly contribute to my academic success and well-being.	1.0	3.8	Agree
3. Challenges or distractions in my learning environment often hinder my academic progress.	1.0	3.5	Agree
4. My learning environment fosters a positive atmosphere for effective learning.	0.9	3.7	Agree
5. The overall setup of my learning environment supports my ability to stay focused and productive during academic activities.	1.0	3.7	Agree
Overall	0.7	3.7	Agree

Table 8 illustrates the level of student engagement in online and remote learning courses. The results indicate that participation in online or remote learning courses, even in part due to circumstances such as the COVID-19 pandemic (M=3.9, SD=1.1), was perceived as accurate. On the other hand, all other statements about online learning were perceived as neutral (overall mean = 3.2, SD=0.6)

Statements	SD	Mean	Description
1. I have participated in online or remote learning courses, even partially, due to circumstances such as the COVID-19 pandemic	1.1	3.9	Agree
2. My experiences with online learning have been more on the positive effect,	0.9	2.8	Neutral
3. The flexibility of online learning has positively impacted my ability to manage my schedule	0.9	3.0	Neutral
4. Interactions with peers and instructors in online courses have been abundant.	0.7	3.1	Neutral
5. Technology-related challenges have significantly hindered my online learning experience. (reverse legend)	0.8	3.4	Disagree
Overall (negative statements was coded in reverse)	0.5	3.0	Neutral

Table 9 shows the perceived effectiveness of the teaching methods employed in helping students learn, retain information, and align themselves with their preferred learning style. All statements regarding the teaching methods were perceived as effective (overall mean = 3.8, SD=0.8).

Statements	SD	Mean	Description
1. The teaching methods or approaches employed have been highly effective in helping me learn and retain information.	0.9	3.8	Agree
2. I believe that the teaching methods in place contribute positively to my learning and retention of information.	0.9	3.8	Agree
3. The teaching methods used align well with my preferred learning style.	0.9	3.5	Agree
4. The variety of teaching methods appeals to different learning styles, promoting a more engaging learning experience	2.1	3.9	Agree
5. Teaching methods in my educational institution actively encourage student participation and engagement	1.0	3.7	Agree
Overall	0.8	3.8	Agree

Table 10 shows the students' perceived use of technology in their education and the extent to which they believe it enhances their learning experience. They perceived a positive contribution from technology to education (overall mean = 3.4; SD=0.6).

Statements	SD	Mean	Description
1. I have an incredibly positive perception of the use of technology (e.g., online tools, educational apps) in my education	0.9	3.6	Agree
2. I hold a positive view of how technology enhances my learning experience	0.9	3.7	Agree

3. My learning experience is significantly enhanced by the integration of technology in education	0.9	3.5	Agree
4. Specific technology tools or platforms positively contribute to my understanding and engagement in learning	0.8	3.8	Agree
5. I have encountered technology tools or platforms that have negatively impacted my learning experience (reverse legend)	1.0	3.4	Disagree
Overall (negative statements was coded in reverse)	0.6	3.4	Agree

Qualitative Aspects

Thematic Analysis (Students)

Learning environment conducive to academic success and well-being

Theme	Description
Physical Environment	A well-organized and comfortable physical space, free of clutter and well-lit, is essential for fostering concentration and efficiency during study sessions.
Access to Educational Resources	The availability and accessibility of educational resources, including a well-equipped library, online databases, and relevant course materials, contribute to comprehensive learning.
Integration of Technology	The integration of technology, including high-speed internet, up-to-date software, and interactive learning tools, enhances the educational experience, making it dynamic and engaging.
Social Support	A supportive social environment, built through interactions with peers, professors, and mentors, is imperative for both academic and emotional well-being.
Flexibility and Autonomy	Flexibility in the learning schedule and autonomy to explore personal interests contribute significantly, fostering a sense of ownership over one's education and enhancing motivation.
Inclusive and Diverse Environment	An inclusive and diverse academic environment, exposing individuals to varied perspectives and ideas, enhances critical thinking and prepares them for a globalized world.

Health and Wellness Initiatives	The integration of health and wellness initiatives, including access to fitness facilities, mental health resources, and programs promoting a healthy work-life balance, is vital for well-being.
Quality of Teaching Methodologies	The quality of teaching methodologies, incorporating varied instructional approaches catering to diverse learning styles, is a key determinant of academic success.
Feedback and Evaluation Systems	A robust system for feedback and evaluation, providing constructive feedback from peers and instructors, aids in identifying areas for improvement and promotes continuous learning.
Extracurricular Engagement	Beyond the academic curriculum, opportunities for extracurricular activities, such as participation in clubs, sports, or cultural events, contribute to a well-rounded education.

This analysis highlights critical aspects of the learning environment that contribute to academic success and well-being. A well-organized physical space, access to educational resources, integration of technology, and social support are foundational. Flexibility, autonomy, and inclusive environments fosters a sense of ownership and readiness. Health and wellness initiatives, quality teaching methodologies, and effective feedback systems are vital for holistic development. Extracurricular engagement beyond academics enriches overall educational experience. This synthesis underscores the interconnected nature of these elements, emphasizing the need for a comprehensive approach to create a supportive and enriching learning environment.

Challenges or distractions related to technical issues in the learning environment.

Theme	Description
Technical Infrastructure Challenges	- Slow internet connectivity and malfunctioning devices are identified as pervasive issues.
Disruption to Online Learning	- Technical glitches disrupt the seamless flow of online learning and research activities.
Impact on Research Activities	- Challenges with technological infrastructure hinder research activities, potentially impacting the quality and depth of research conducted.

Universal Nature of Challenges	- The repetition of the issue across multiple responses highlights the universality of these challenges, suggesting a widespread impact on the learning environment.
Need for Technological Solutions	- The prevalence of technical challenges underscores the need for effective technological solutions to ensure a smooth learning experience.

This analysis revealed the consistent technical challenges in the learning environment. Slow Internet connectivity and malfunctioning devices are pervasive issues that disrupt the seamless flow of online learning and hinder research activities. The universal nature of these challenges, evident through their repetition across multiple responses, suggests their widespread impact on the learning environment. These findings emphasize the critical need for effective technological solutions to address these challenges and to ensure a smooth and productive learning experience for students.

Online Learning Experiences

Theme	Description
Advantages of Online Learning	
Flexibility of Scheduling	Online learning provides the individual with the flexibility to schedule study hours according to their peak productivity times, allowing for a personalized and efficient learning experience.
Access to Digital Resources	The wealth of digital resources available online facilitates comprehensive research, offering a broader range of materials compared to traditional learning methods.
Disadvantages of Online Learning	
Technical Issues	Online learning presents challenges such as internet connectivity problems or platform glitches, occasionally disrupting the learning experience.
Lack of Face-to-Face Interaction	The absence of face-to-face interaction is noted as a drawback, impacting the depth of social connections and the immediacy of feedback from instructors.

Advantages of Online Learning

Flexibility of Scheduling

Online learning is a versatile and accessible learning method. Individuals have benefited from scheduling flexibility, which allows them to tailor their study hours to the peak productivity times. This flexibility enables learners to create personalized timetables, accommodate various responsibilities, and optimize their learning efficiency.

Access to Digital Resources

Additionally, the wealth of digital resources available online has facilitated comprehensive research. Compared to traditional learning methods, online platforms offer a broader range of materials, including articles, videos, and interactive simulations. This wealth of resources enhances the depth and breadth of learning and provides diverse perspectives on the subjects studied.

Disadvantages of Online Learning

Technical Issues

However, despite these advantages, online learning presents several challenges. Technical issues such as Internet connectivity problems or platform glitches occasionally disrupt learning experiences. Such disruptions can hinder the flow of the learning process and create frustration among individuals.

Lack of Face-to-Face Interaction

Another notable drawback is the absence of face-to-face interaction. In a traditional classroom setting, students benefit from direct communication with instructors and peers, fostering a sense of community and providing immediate feedback. Online learning that lacks this physical presence may limit the depth of social connections and affect the immediacy of feedback from instructors.

Effective Teaching Methods

Theme	Description
Diversity of Instructional Modalities	
Visual Aids, Multimedia Presentations, and Interactive Discussions	Diverse instructional modalities, including visual aids, multimedia presentations, and interactive discussions, have proven to be impactful. The incorporation of different learning styles ensured a more comprehensive understanding of the material. This approach caters to individual preferences and allows for a personalized

	learning experience, contributing to better information retention.
Teaching Methods Involving Feedback and Assessments	
Regular Feedback on Assignments, Quizzes, and Exams	Teaching methods that involve regular feedback and assessments play a crucial role in the learning process. Timely feedback on assignments, quizzes, and exams helps the individual gauge their understanding of the material, identify areas for improvement, and adapt their study strategies accordingly. This iterative feedback loop enhances the retention of information in the long term.

Diversity of Instructional Modalities

Visual Aids, Multimedia Presentations, and Interactive Discussions

Diverse instructional modalities, including visual aids, multimedia presentations, and interactive discussions, have proven to be impactful. The incorporation of different learning styles ensured a more comprehensive understanding of these materials. This approach caters to individual preferences and allows for a personalized learning experience, contributing to better information retention.

Teaching Methods Involving Feedback and Assessments

Regular Feedback on Assignments, Quizzes, and Exams

Teaching methods that involve regular feedback and assessments play a crucial role in the learning process. Timely feedback on assignments, quizzes, and exams helps individuals gauge their understanding of material. This allowed them to identify areas for improvement and to adapt their study strategies accordingly. This iterative feedback loop enhances long-term information retention.

Teaching Methods that Need Improvement

Theme	Description
Integration of Technology	

Seamless Incorporation into the Curriculum	The individual identifies the need to improve the integration of technology within educational institutions. While acknowledging the importance of technology in contemporary learning, there is a call for enhancing its seamless incorporation into the curriculum. This includes providing adequate training for both educators and students to navigate digital platforms effectively, ensuring a smoother and more productive online learning experience.
Adequate Training for Educators and Students	There is a recognition that adequate training for both educators and students is essential for effective use of technology. The lack of proficiency in navigating digital platforms may hinder the overall learning experience.
Diversification of Teaching Styles	
Catering to Diverse Learning Preferences	A perceived need for greater diversification of teaching styles within the educational institution is identified. The current teaching methods may not cater to the diverse learning preferences of all the students. There is a call for a more inclusive approach that incorporates a variety of instructional modalities, such as project-based learning, collaborative activities, and experiential learning. This could better accommodate different learning styles and enhance overall understanding and retention of information.
Conclusion	
Addressing Technological Integration and Diversity	In conclusion, the identified areas for improvement revolve around addressing the integration of technology and diversification of teaching styles. Ensuring the seamless incorporation of technology into the curriculum with proper training for both educators and students is crucial. Simultaneously, adopting a more inclusive approach to teaching that accommodates diverse learning preferences through various instructional modalities is deemed necessary for enhancing overall understanding and retention of information.

Integration of Technology

Seamless Incorporation into the Curriculum

Individuals identify a need to improve the integration of technology within educational institutions. Acknowledges the importance of technology in contemporary learning. Calls to enhance seamless incorporation into the curriculum.

Adequate Training for Educators and Students

Adequate training of educators and students is essential for effective use of technology. Lack of proficiency in navigating digital platforms may hinder the overall learning experience.

Diversification of Teaching Styles

Catering to Diverse Learning Preferences

Perceived need for greater diversification of teaching styles within educational institutions. Current teaching methods may not cater to the diverse learning preferences of all the students. Calls for a more inclusive approach incorporating various instructional modalities.

Technology Tools and Platforms Impacting Learning Experience

Theme	Description
Positive Impactful Technology	
Effective Learning Tools	Individuals have experienced positive impacts from specific technology tools or platforms in their learning journey. While specific examples are not provided, it is evident that certain technologies have contributed positively to the learning experience.
Negative Impactful Technology	
Challenges with Learning Management System (LMS)	The individual has encountered challenges with the Learning Management System (LMS) used in their educational institution. The LMS, intended to streamline course content and assignments, is noted for its complexity and occasional technical limitations. These issues have led to frustration and disruption in the learning process, highlighting the need for

	improvements in the usability and reliability of the chosen LMS.
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Positive Impactful Technology

Effective Learning Tools

Individuals experience positive effects from specific technological tools or platforms during their learning journeys. Specific examples are not provided, but it is evident that certain technologies have contributed positively to the learning experience.

Negative Impactful Technology

Challenges with Learning Management System (LMS)

Individuals encounter challenges in the learning management systems (LMS) used in their educational institutions. The LMS, intended to streamline course content and assignments, was noted for its complexity and technical limitations. These issues have led to frustration and disruption in the learning process, highlighting the need to improve the usability and reliability of selected LMS.

Thematic Analysis (Teachers)

Effective Teaching Methods for Student Engagement

Teaching Method/Strategy	Description	Elaboration
Active Discussion and Engaging Use of Technology	- Fostering interactive discussions. - Integrating technology (laptops, tablets) for research and online activities.	- Dynamic and engaging learning environment.
Motivation Mastery of the Lesson	- Emphasizing motivation and mastery of the lesson. - Use of visual aids like TV and PowerPoint (PPT). - Administering quizzes for improvement.	- Motivational strategies to enhance lesson delivery. - Aligning lessons through visual aids. - Quizzes for continuous improvement.

Brainstorming for Knowledge and Practical Experience	- Utilizing brainstorming to gauge knowledge and practical experience.	- Assessing understanding through interactive brainstorming sessions.
Incorporation of Games, Traditional, and Modern Methods	- Using a combination of games, traditional, and modern methods. - Integrating technology (laptop, TV, speakers, projectors).	- Engagement through diverse methods. - Concerns about potential disengagement during presentations.
Discovery and Collaborative Techniques	- Implementing discovery methods (induction, demonstration). - Encouraging collaborative techniques for active participation.	- Active student participation through discovery and collaboration. - Acknowledgment of challenges related to internet connectivity and power supply.
Collaborative Activities and Engagement	- Emphasizing collaborative activities. - Use of PowerPoint (PPT) with videos.	- Facilitating collaborative activities with multimedia support. - Challenges in creating appealing and informative PowerPoint presentations.
Interactive Activities and Real-World Examples	- Utilizing interactive or gamified PowerPoint (PPT). - Incorporating real-world examples for exploration.	- Enhancing engagement through interactive presentations. - Challenges related to material availability.
Group Activities for Unlocking Difficulties	- Using group activities for unlocking difficulties. - Incorporating deductive and inductive methods. - Utilizing laptops and computers.	- Unlocking difficulties through group activities. - Addressing challenges related to poor internet connectivity.
Professional Development and Training	- Participating in professional development activities (regional training, webinars).	- Enhancing teaching skills through ongoing professional development. - The specific impact on teaching is not detailed.

A thematic analysis of teaching methods revealed a diverse range of strategies employed by educators. Active discussions on technology integration, motivation mastery using visual aids, and incorporation of games and modern methods are emphasized. Brainstorming for knowledge assessment, collaborative techniques, and real-world examples are also prevalent. Challenges related to technology, such as poor Internet connectivity, underscore the need for infrastructure support. Additionally, the importance of ongoing professional development through activities such as regional training and webinars has been recognized. Despite effective strategies, the responses highlighted the continual need for adaptation and improvement to address challenges and enhance overall teaching experience.

Types of technology used in teaching and their benefits.

Technology	Usage	Benefits
Laptop, Tablets	Research and engaging online class activities	Enhances student involvement and provides a platform for dynamic, interactive learning.
TV, PPT	Presentation of information	Effectively conveys content in a visually appealing manner, aiding in comprehension.
PPT	Visual aid in presentations	Facilitates organized and visually appealing lessons, improving the understanding of complex topics.
Laptop, TV, Speakers, Projectors	Utilized for various teaching activities	Enhances the audio-visual aspects of teaching, making lessons more engaging and interactive.
PPT with Videos	Visual aid and multimedia integration	Combines visual and auditory elements for a richer learning experience, catering to different learning styles.
Interactive or Gamified PPT	Engaging presentations with interactive elements	Makes learning enjoyable and interactive, fostering active participation and comprehension.
Video Clips	Incorporation into lessons for diverse subjects	Provides real-world examples, enhancing understanding and making lessons more relatable.

Laptops, Computers, Applications	Diverse applications in teaching and learning	Enables a versatile approach, utilizing various tools for different aspects of the educational process.
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A thematic analysis of technology usage in teaching highlights the variety of tools employed by educators. Laptops and tablets are used for research and engaging in online class activities to enhance student involvement. The use of TV and PowerPoint (PPT) is recurrent, indicating their effectiveness in conveying information. PPT, along with videos, is a prevalent choice for visual aids, and contributes to a dynamic learning environment. The incorporation of interactive or gamified PPT adds an engaging dimension to lessons. The consistent use of video clips underscores their role in facilitating understanding. A broad spectrum of technologies, including laptops, computers, and video applications, provides versatile teaching approaches. Overall, the responses emphasized the significant role of diverse technologies in enhancing teaching and learning experiences.

Students' reference

Theme	Key Points
Alignment of Lessons	- Internet references are used to align lessons with additional online resources.
Enhancing Engagement	- Providing internet references is seen to encourage active engagement in the learning process.
Facilitating Exploration	- Internet references are used to prompt students to explore topics independently, fostering a deeper understanding.
Supporting Classroom Discussion	- References are given to compensate for potential forgetfulness of classroom discussions, reinforcing concepts outside the classroom setting.
Ease of Access	- Internet references are provided to allow students easy access to information, acknowledging the practicality of the digital learning environment.
Encouraging Independent Thinking	- Internet references aim to give students new ideas and promote independent thinking and critical analysis.
Subject-specific References	- References are tailored to the specific subject, ensuring relevance and optimization of the learning experience.

Thematic analysis reveals that the decision to give students references from the Internet is motivated by a combination of pedagogical considerations, a desire to enhance engagement, and an acknowledgment of the evolving learning landscape. Educators leverage online resources to align lessons, support classroom discussions, facilitate exploration, and encourage independent thinking. The responses reflect a nuanced understanding of the role of Internet references in modern education, emphasizing the importance of a dynamic and inclusive approach to teaching and learning.

Challenges and concerns encountered when using technology for teaching.

Theme	Key Points
Technical Difficulties	- Equipment malfunctions can disrupt the flow of discussion.
	- Concerns about maintaining an easy elaboration of lessons.
Internet Connectivity	- Access to good internet is crucial for effective teaching.
	- Students may disengage if there are issues with internet connectivity.
	- Connectivity issues can affect students' ability to listen or take notes, especially if relying on slides.
	- Consistent challenges with internet connection and power supply.
PowerPoint Presentation Concerns	- Questions about making PowerPoint presentations both appealing and informative.
Lack of Material Availability	- Concerns about the availability of materials for teaching.
Poor Internet Connectivity	- Multiple mentions of poor internet quality affecting teaching.

This table summarizes the identified themes and key points related to the challenges and concerns faced when incorporating technology into teaching. These issues range from technical difficulties and Internet connectivity problems to concerns about maintaining student engagement, and the appeal and informativeness of presentations. Additionally, there are mentions of the challenges related to the availability of teaching materials.

Assessment methods are typically used to evaluate students' progress.

Theme	Key Points
Quizzes and Exams	- Regular use of quizzes and exams as assessment methods.
	- Administering quizzes after lessons for ongoing evaluation.
	- Recognition that giving quizzes post-lesson can improve teaching capability.
Performance Tasks	- Utilization of performance tasks as a form of assessment.
	- Integration of different types of assessments, including essays, identification tests, true or false, and multiple-choice.
Projects	- Inclusion of projects as a method to assess students' progress.
Variety of Assessments	- Use of a combination of quizzes, exams, performance tasks, research, reaction papers, and summarization of concepts.
Written Assessment	- Emphasis on written performance tasks, reports, and discussions as assessment tools.
Daily Performance	- Consideration of daily performance as part of the assessment process.
Video Presentations	- Assessment through students presenting topics via video.
Quarterly Assessment	- Inclusion of quarterly assessments for a broader evaluation of learning progress.
Word Problems	- Use of word problems in written assessments.

This table provides an overview of the thematic analysis, highlighting the variety of assessment methods used by educators. These themes include traditional approaches such as quizzes and exams as well as a diverse range of assessment methods such as performance tasks, projects, written assessments, and the integration of distinct types of quizzes. Emphasis on ongoing assessments and a mix of evaluation techniques was evident in the responses.

How assessment practices can be improved to better support student learning and growth

Theme	Key Points
Developing Critical Thinking Skills	- Practicing learning to help students develop critical thinking skills.
Knowledge Verification	- The belief that assessment is necessary to verify what students have learned.
Immediate Post-Lesson Assessment	- Conducting assessments immediately after the lesson to test student understanding.
Continuous Improvement through Research	- Continuous research and training to improve assessment practices.
Assessment Score as Learning Indicator	- Viewing the score of assessments as an indicator of students' learning and growth.
Improvement of Assessment Techniques	- Strong belief in the need to improve assessment techniques.
Regular Monitoring for Learning Progress	- Providing regular monitoring of learning progress after assessments.
Identifying Weaknesses and Improving	- Assessments help identify weaknesses and strengths, facilitating targeted teaching to fill learning gaps.
Variety of Methods in Formative Assessment	- Improvement by incorporating a variety of methods, including formative assessment.
Lifelong Learning and Assessment	- Assessment practices aimed at fostering lifelong learning.

This table summarizes the thematic analysis, showing a range of beliefs about how assessment practices can be enhanced to better support student learning and growth. The identified themes included the importance of critical thinking, necessity of assessments for knowledge verification, timing of assessments, continuous improvement through research, role of assessment scores, need for improvement in assessment techniques, regular monitoring of progress, targeted teaching based on assessment results, use of various formative assessment methods, and the alignment of assessment practices with lifelong learning goals.

Participation in professional development activities related to teaching using technology in the past year.

Theme	Key Points
No Participation	- Multiple responses indicating no participation in professional development activities related to teaching with technology in the past year.
Limited Information	- Some responses provide minimal information, stating "none," "not yet" or "not yet" making it unclear if there was a lack of opportunities or if the individual did not participate.
Yes, Webinars and Training	- Positive responses indicating participation in professional development activities such as regional training in science, webinars, etc.
	- Acknowledgment of engagement in webinars as a specific form of professional development.
General Affirmative Responses	- Affirmative responses without specific details about the nature and impact of the professional development experiences.

This table summarizes the thematic analysis, highlighting the prevalence of non-participation in professional development related to teaching with technology in the past year. Among those who participated, there was a mention of engaging in webinars, regional training in science, and other unspecified activities. The impact of these experiences on teaching is not explicitly described in the responses provided.

DISCUSSION

Quantitative and qualitative data provide a comprehensive overview of teacher and student profiles, their perceptions of various aspects of the educational environment, and the integration of technology into teaching and learning. These findings highlight several key points, which require further investigation.

Teacher and Student Profiles

The distribution of teacher respondents across schools in Isabela reflects diverse representations, thus ensuring a broad perspective of the educational landscape.

Many female teachers belonging to the middle-adult age group may influence their teaching styles and approaches, as these demographics often bring unique perspectives and experiences into the classroom.

The focus on junior high schools (JHS) and the significant percentage of teachers with 10 years of teaching experience or less indicate a dynamic teaching environment, possibly with a mix of experienced educators and those early in their careers.

For students, representation from various schools, especially those with a high concentration in specific institutions, offers insight into the learning experiences of diverse groups.

The majority were female, aged 17-18 years, and in grade 12, shedding light on the demographics of the student population, which may influence their preferences and learning needs.

Teaching Methods and Technology Integration

The overwhelmingly positive perception of teaching methods by teachers, with a mean of 4.8 out of 5, indicates a strong consensus on their effectiveness. This alignment is crucial in creating a cohesive and impactful teaching environment.

The universal daily integration of technology by all teachers suggests a commitment to remaining technologically relevant to the rapidly evolving educational landscape.

Impact of Technology on Learning

Teachers acknowledge the strong positive impact of technology on various aspects of student learning, including understanding, engagement, and critical thinking, and emphasize the pivotal role of technology in enhancing educational experience.

The positive perception of students towards technology in education aligns with teachers' beliefs, indicating the mutual recognition of their value.

Challenges Faced

The thematic analysis of challenges faced by both students and teachers, such as technical difficulties, slow Internet connectivity, and issues with the Learning Management System (LMS), underscores the need for a robust technological infrastructure and ongoing support.

Conclusions

This study has the potential to greatly enhance the field of education by demonstrating the positive effects of innovative pedagogical methods and technological integration on contemporary learning. By employing a mixed-methods approach, this study provides a comprehensive understanding of both the quantitative and qualitative aspects of the teaching and learning environments. This approach allowed for a thorough examination of the perceptions of both educators and students, emphasizing the

effectiveness of current teaching methods and widespread incorporation of technology in the classroom. This study significantly advances the current knowledge by providing empirical evidence of the advantages and challenges associated with technological integration in education. The key findings of this study reveal that both educators and students recognize the positive impact of technology on learning, despite facing technical issues and varying online learning experiences. Quantitative data, supported by qualitative insights, provide a detailed picture of the current educational landscape, highlighting effective teaching methods and areas that need improvement.

Future research should focus on several key areas, including the long-term impact of technology on learning outcomes and how sustained use of technology in education affects student performance over time; the effectiveness of professional development programs in supporting innovative pedagogical practices; personalized online learning experiences to cater to individual student needs; the impact of enhanced technological infrastructure on teaching effectiveness and student engagement; and the relationship between student well-being and the physical and technological aspects of the learning environment. By addressing these areas, future studies can build on the findings of this research, further advancing the field of education and contributing to the development of more effective and inclusive educational practices.

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